

A systematic approach for horizontal and vertical scale up of sintered Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites for Aerospace – Advances and perspectives

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Abstract

Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites (UHTCMCs) are the next generation composites developed for application in the harsh environment of aerospace. Qualification of these materials requires the manufacturing of demonstrators for testing in relevant environments, which in turn, requires to scale them up. This paper illustrates the systematic approach followed for the scale-up of UHTCMCs, obtained by sintering, based on carbon fibre reinforced zirconium diboride plus silicon carbide ceramic matrix composites ($ZrB_2/SiC/C_f$) from laboratory to industrial scale dimensions. The scale-up process covered a period of three years and concerned not only an increase in diameter of ~10 times (from 40 to 400 mm), but also an increase in thickness of ~30 times (from 5 to 160 mm). Small-scale products were consolidated by hot pressing in the laboratories of the Institute of Science and Technology for Ceramics (ISTEC), whilst larger samples were consolidated by an industrial spark plasma sintering facility. After each scale-up step, samples were extracted from the manufacture to check reproducibility in terms of composition, microstructure, and properties. Thanks to the homogenous fibre distribution and sapient dosing of secondary phases, composites with different diameters and thickness were successfully consolidated by both techniques with little adjustment of sintering parameters up to the maximum size of available industrial furnaces. The

large discs produced allowed production of 170 mm long bars for tensile testing and large tiles for hypersonic wind tunnel tests. Thick samples were useful to machine complex shapes such as screws and nuts, vertical bars for characterization of properties along the composite thickness and nozzle demonstrators.

Keywords: scale-up; sintering, microstructure design; superior mechanical properties; aerospace components; ceramic matrix composites;

1. Introduction

When traveling at Mach 5 or higher speeds, the strong heat generated by air in the atmosphere can compromise the structural integrity of hypersonic vehicles. Corrosive gases and particles impact their surface, and the temperature affecting the vehicle's outer contours can rise above 2000 °C, causing oxidation and ablation of surface layers [1]. Thermal Protection Systems (TPS) must withstand these extreme temperatures and intense mechanical vibration during ascent into orbit or re-entry from space. Going to an even harsher environment, rocket engine nozzles must withstand extreme mechanical and thermochemical conditions, with temperatures exceeding 2500 °C [2]. In addition, next-generation rocket engines will need to be even better performing to withstand new propellants that can produce more thrust and carry larger loads. Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) are the only materials designed to survive critical mechanical stresses and high thermal shocks, but temperatures above 1600–1700 °C are still an operational limit for their use [3–6].

UHTCMCs are a special class of ceramic matrix composites composed of ultra-refractory matrices [7] and carbon fibres (C_f) or preforms [8,9]. These materials have been widely studied and developed during the H2020 EU project C³harme (Next Generation Ceramic Composites for Harsh Environment and Space, GA n. 685594) for application in Aerospace as thermal protection systems and cooling-free nozzle inserts. Researchers of the present work have proposed an innovative approach, where the carbon fibre cloths are homogeneously integrated into an ultra-refractory sintered ceramic matrix. Neither coating is applied to the fibre, nor external thermal barrier coating (TBC) is applied. Sintering of these UHTCMCs through methods typical of bulk ceramic science (e.g. hot pressing (HP), spark plasma sintering (SPS) [10]) is the key

processing step that distinguishes these non-oxide/ C_f composites UHTCMCs from their predecessors.

Sintering is a very fast technique that allows the densification of these CMCs in one single thermal treatment occurring in few hours, with the only disadvantage of geometrical limitation to planar forms when a mechanical pressure is applied. The one-shot densification represents an enormous advantage with respect to time consuming techniques such as chemical vapour infiltration (CVI), [11] or even polymer infiltration and pyrolysis (PIP). The use of water-based slurries instead of volatile organic compounds and/or liquid chemical precursors makes this process eco-friendly compared to other conventional techniques requiring repetitive and environmentally not-friendly debonding cycles.

Previous works have already identified the several steps involved in the development of these composites, such as the design of matrix compositions, development of new processes including manual fibre preform impregnation or filament winding [12], densification of the composites through hot pressing or spark plasma sintering [10], mechanical characterization at room and elevated temperature, oxidation studies from 1500 to 2100 °C and arc jet tests in plasma wind tunnel facilities [10,13–16]. Results obtained have shown that similar microstructures and properties can be achieved by HP and SPS, with a reduction of temperature and processing time in case of SPS [17,18].

Qualification of these new materials requires the manufacturing of demonstrators for testing in relevant environment, which in turn, requires to scale-them up. To date, few reports are available on scale-up of UHTCMCs. In the open scientific literature, as far as we know, typical dimensions of UHTCMCs samples are 50-300 mm on plain [19,20] and 4-20 mm of thickness [21–23], and do not exceed 45 mm of thickness [24]. Two U.S. companies produce large CMC components containing UHTC phases, e.g. Ultramet [www.ultramet.com] and Matech [www.matechgsm.com], while the European company of Airbus (former EADS) is studying the UHTC enrichment of the SICARBON™ [21,25].

In order to demonstrate the potential of UHTCMC materials for being used as an external surface component of a thermal protection system, a TPS panel was designed according to real vehicle missions, the SHEFEX I and II missions, flown in 2005 and 2012 [26][21]. On both vehicles, the TPS was made from flat C/C-SiC panels which were attached to the vehicle structure via fixation elements, screws and nuts, made from the same material [27]. Therefore, the proposed design included a large UHTCMC tile with a width of 194 mm, a length of 240 mm and thickness 4 mm, integration elements, such as stand-offs, screws and nuts,

made of UHTCMC, and other insulation elements. A sketch of the model holder is provided in Fig. 1. In parallel, the demonstration of the possible use of UHTCMCs composites as nozzle inserts required the development of thick manufacture, e.g. a scale-up in thickness from few millimeters to almost 20 cm.

In this work, for the first time, we showed the sequential scale-up of UHTCMCs, including:

- increase of diameter (D) from 40 to 170 and to 400 mm discs, with thickness (H) of 5 mm.
- increase of thickness (H) from 5 mm to 45 mm, with 40 mm diameter (D).
- increase in thickness (H) from 45 mm to 160 mm and diameter (D) of 170 mm.

In order to produce pieces large enough for obtaining the final demonstrators, UHTCMCs green pieces were densified in one of the largest machines available in Europe, the model H-HP D 400 (FCT Systeme GmbH, Germany), that allows to reach 400 mm diameter. For each scale-up step, microstructural features and basic mechanical properties were determined and compared. As a case study, the 0/90° configuration of unidirectional fibre cloths was selected.

In addition to technological results, this study also includes scientific aspects such as study of the sintering mechanisms, evaluation of mechanical properties under a variety of processing conditions and assessment of reproducibility and mechanical characterization along the UHTCMC thickness.

Fig. 1. Details of the assembly for the large tile tests, a) assembly without side plates, b) interior set-up showing connections to the base plane through UHTCMC standoffs, screws and nuts c) sketches of nozzle inserts. Quotes are in mm. Courtesy of AVIO SpA.

2. Material and Methods

The following raw materials were used: - ZrB_2 (Grade B, H.C. Starck, Germany), SiC (Grade UF-25, H.C. Starck, Germany) and commercial unidirectional carbon pitch fibre cloths (G. Angeloni, Italy)).

For the matrix of UHTCMCs, ZrB_2 /SiC powder mixtures were prepared by wet ball milling and drying. With these mixtures, water-based slurries were prepared, according to previous works [12]. The composites were fabricated infiltrating the UD fabrics with the slurries by hand lay-up and subsequently stacking layers in $0/90^\circ$ configuration (Fig. 2a). The dimension of the green impregnated preforms was increased gradually from few millimetres to squared panels of $400\text{ mm} \times 400\text{ mm}$. The scale-up scheme is summarized in Fig. 2b. During the long-term series of experiments carried out some adjustments were necessary, such as increase of fibre volumetric content to decrease the final density and revision of the sintering parameters when passing from one furnace to another.

Fig. 2. a) Sketch of the process for UHTCMC fabrication and b) rationale of the scale-up for UHTCMCs materials.

Scale-up in diameter: The first part of this work was concerned with the investigation of sintering conditions on lab-scale samples, 30-50 mm, with the two techniques, Hot Pressing and Spark Plasma Sintering (Step 1,2). This work was illustrated in reference [10], for manufactures with a 0/0° stacking sequence and showed a quite good reproducibility between the two techniques. The subsequent steps (Step 3 and Step 4) of scale-up manufacturing were carried out in the hybrid SPS furnace H-HP D 400 (FCT Systeme GmbH, Germany), increasing the diameter of 0/90° samples from 40-50 to 170 mm, and from 170 to 400 mm, maintaining a thickness of about 5 mm. The sintering of 400 mm large discs (**SPd400**) was carried out at the same temperature of 170 mm disc (**SPd170**), but a reduced mechanical pressure and lower heating rate were necessary, due to intrinsic limitations of the machine for such large diameters. The final disc was sectioned

in different positions to extract samples for mechanical characterization. Both microstructure and mechanical properties were analysed.

Scale-up in thickness. First, four cylinders 45 mm high/50 mm diameter (**HPH45**) were prepared and sintered by hot pressing adopting the same sintering conditions of the small disc (Step 2*). After microstructure analysis to assess the good level of adhesion between the layers, 45 mm high/170 mm wide cylinders (Step 3*, **SPh45**) were assembled and sintered directly by the Hybrid SPS at the same conditions adopted for Step 3, sample **SPd170**. Two cylinders of such dimensions were produced and were analysed in terms of microstructure, again to check the good level of adhesion between the layers. Finally, for the first time, a huge cylinders (**SPh160**) was prepared assembling about 500 layers to reach a final height of 160 mm, for 170 mm of diameter (step 4*). The thermal cycle was the same of the 45 mm thick blocks, **SPh45-a,b** in Table 1.

The microstructures were analysed on polished and fractured surfaces by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Carl Zeiss Sigma NTS GmbH Oberkochen, Germany) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK). After sintering, the bulk density was determined by the Archimede's method. The relative density, ρ was calculated as the ratio of experimental to theoretical value, and residual porosity deduced as $1 - \rho$. The theoretical density of the materials was calculated using the rule of mixtures based on the starting compositions. For the scaled-up manufactures, samples were extracted in different positions to check for microstructural homogeneity. Chemical reactions occurring during sintering were investigated using the HSC chemistry 6.1 software package.

The following mechanical properties were measured on selected manufactures:

- Young's modulus (E) and shear modulus (G) were measured using the resonance frequency method (ASTM E1875 – 08) on 60 mm \times 10 mm \times 2.5 mm bars (length, width, and thickness) using an H&P gain-phase analyzer (Tokyo, Japan) at RT. 6 bars were tested.
- Flexural strength (σ_f) was tested by 3-point bending at room temperature and 1800 °C on 60 mm \times 10 mm \times 2.5 mm (length, width, and thickness) bars of **SPd170**, **SPd400** and **SPh160**, with crosshead speed 8 mm/min and according to EN 658–3:2002 standard. Having not enough available material to fabricate such large specimens from small manufactures (**HPd50**, **HPH45**), 25 mm \times 2.5 mm \times 2 mm (length, width, and thickness) bars were tested by 4-point bending at room temperature with a lower span of 20 mm

and an upper span of 10 mm and at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min, according to ISO 14704:2016. 25 mm × 2.5 mm × 2 mm and 60 mm × 10 mm × 2.5 mm bars were machined along the thickness of samples **HPh45** and **SPh160** to test the 4-pt bending strength along the sample thickness. Room temperature tests were carried out in a Zwick-Roell testing machine at CNR. High temperature tests at 1800 °C were carried out in the INDUTHERM machine available at German Aerospace Centre (DLR) with C_f/C–SiC CMC fixture for tests in argon flux. Three bars were tested for each temperature point. For sake of comparison between 3-point and 4-point bending tests, the stress (σ) and the strain (ε) were calculated according to the following equations:

$$\sigma_{3pt.} = \frac{3Fs}{2wt^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{3pt.} = \frac{6Dt}{s^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{4pt.} = \frac{3Fs}{4wt^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{4pt.} = \frac{4.36Dt}{s^2} \quad (4)$$

where F is the force, s is outer support span, w and t are the specimen width and thickness, respectively, and D is the deflection.

- Dog bone shaped bars were machined from the large diameter disc (**SPd400**), for testing tensile strength (σ_t) at room and elevated temperature according to the sketch in supplementary information (Fig. S1), specifically developed for these new composites. Except for the specimen geometry, the tests followed the EN 658–1:1999 norm for tests at room temperature and the ISO 14574:2013 norm for tests at high temperature. The room temperature tensile tests were carried out in the Zwick-Roell 1475, a standard mechanical test machine. The elevated temperature tests were carried out at 1600 °C/1800°C in a special high-temperature testing facility, called INDUTHERM and available at DLR.

- For the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE), the relative dimensional change ($\Delta L/L_0$) vs temperature was recorded up to 1300 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, under flowing argon, using a Netzsch dilatometer (mod. DIL E 402, Netzsch Gerätebau, Germany), on 2 bars of 25.0 mm × 2.0 mm × 2.5 mm (length, width, and thickness). The linear CTE (α) was determined as the slope of the secant line joining the values at RT and 1300°C.

-Thermal conductivity (k_{th}) was obtained using the following equation:

$$k_{th}(T) = \rho(T) \cdot C_p(T) \cdot D_{th}(T) \quad (5)$$

where k_{th} is expressed in W/(m K), ρ is the bulk density expressed in g/cm³, C_p is the specific heat in J/(g K) and D_{th} is the thermal diffusivity in mm²/s. D_{th} was measured up to 1950 °C under flowing Argon on a 10 mm diameter specimen with 2 mm height using a Netzsch laser flash diffusivity apparatus (mod. 427, Netzsch Geraetebau, Germany). C_p was measured up to 1500 °C using a Netzsch differential scanning calorimeter (mod. DSC 404 F1 Pegasus®, Netzsch Geraetebau, Germany).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructural features of scaled-up components

Fig. 3 shows the as-sintered manufactures, whilst data concerning dimensions, compositions and densities are summarized in Table 1. The targeted fibre content was around 50 vol%, therefore deviations from this value were due to the fluctuation of the process parameters involved, including complexity of the entire process, the different furnaces used and the different types of fibre cloths. Typical microstructures of samples produced are illustrated in Fig. 4. The basic microstructure/texture of the of the lab-scale samples to be replicated in large manufactures consisted in a nearly fully dense ZrB₂/SiC matrix, with homogeneously distributed carbon fibres. The architecture was very regular: dense layers with both 0/0° and 0/90° disposal were stacked showing no voids or delamination. The densities were intermediate between that of a bulk UHTC (~ 6.1 g/cm³) and of a C/SiC composite, ~ 2 g/cm³, all being < 4 g/cm³.

Scale-up in diameter: The starting samples were lab-scale coupons, labelled as **HPd50-a,b** (Table 1). Fig. 4a shows one of these materials with 40 vol% of fibre content, with a very homogeneous distribution of fibre and matrix materials, a compact matrix characterized by ZrB₂, SiC phases and C residues, containing a minor amount of residual porosity. As previously mentioned, lab-scale samples were densified with similar outcomes using either hot pressing or spark plasma sintering. SPS was much faster in achieving full density of the matrix, but also led to a faster reaction between the fibre and the matrix (microstructure not shown here) [10].

Relevant features of the 170 mm diameter disc (**SPd170**) sintered by SPS are illustrated in Fig. 4b. Very similar characteristics were recorded for this sample, such as density of 3.8 g/cm^3 (see Table 1), fibre volumetric amount estimated by image analysis around 44 vol% and a calculated porosity of $\sim 7.8\%$.

Finally, Fig. 4c shows the microstructure of sample **SPd400**, with a diameter of 400 mm and thickness of 5 mm. Compared to previous samples, a slightly higher fibre content was introduced in the matrix and the texture was more defective due to weaving imperfections in the starting carbon preforms. The final density was 3.5 g/cm^3 , due to the higher fibre concentration compared to **SPd170** (54 vs 44%, respectively). Moreover, the extent of pull-out in the fracture was reduced compared to the **SPd170**, and fibre sections appeared somewhat more degraded in this material.

Fig. 3. Camera pictures of as sintered manufactures. From left to right, Top: **HPd50**, **SPd170**, **SPd400**; bottom: **HPh45**, **SPH45**, **SPh160**. Red circles indicated manufactures whose microstructures are reported in Fig. 4.

Table 1. Dimensions, densities, porosity and fibre volumetric amounts for the sintered pellets.

Sample	Ø (mm)	H (mm)	Sintering technique	$\rho_{\text{perim.}}$ (g/cm ³)	$\rho_{\text{rel.}}$ (g/cm ³)	Porosity (vol%)	Fibre (vol%)
HPd50-a ref. [28]	30	3	HP	3.90	92.0	8.0	40±2
HPd50-b	50	12	HP	3.81	96.2	3.8	50±2
SPd170	170	5	SPS	3.76	92.2	7.8	44±5
SPd400	400	5	SPS	3.51	94.6	5.4	54±5
HPh45-a	50	38	HP	3.67	89.5	10.5	42±5
HPh45-b	50	38	HP	4.02	99.9	0.1	48±2
HPh45-c	34	38	HP	3.70	96.4	3.6	52±2
HPh45-d	34	38	HP	3.86	99.2	0.8	51±2
SPh45-a	170	45	SPS	3.65	95.0	5.0	51±2
SPh45-b	170	45	SPS	3.61	94.9	5.1	51±2
SPh160	170	160	SPS	3.40	90.2	9.8	50±2

These characteristics suggest an over-reacted fibre/matrix interface. It is likely that the reduction of the heating rate prolonged the overall permanence at high temperature. It is well known that in samples with large diameter densified with SPS, heterogeneities in the microstructure of sintered products could be introduced due to thermal gradients produced by the radial heat loss in the mould [18,29]. To this aim, portions of materials were extracted from different positions in the 400 mm large disc, **SPd400**, to monitor the microstructural variations across the sample, see Fig. 5. Overall, the microstructure was quite homogeneous, despite minor differences in matrix densification and fibre/matrix interface.

Fig. 4. Microstructure of samples a) **HPd50**, b) **SPd170**: c) **SPd400**, d) **SPh160**. For each sample, micrographs from left to right show texture, fibre distribution in the matrix, matrix features, fracture surface showing fibre pull-out.

Scale-up in thickness: The final relative densities of small 45 mm high blocks (**HPh45-a,b,c,d**) were in most cases very close, ranging from 96 to 99%, whilst the absolute densities were influenced by the fibre content, Table 1. The microstructure was homogeneous throughout the height of the sample (not shown). Two larger cylinders of the same thickness but larger diameter (170 mm) were prepared and sintered by SPS, overlapping more than 100 layers, (samples labelled **SPh45a,b**). The sintered materials had densities of about 3.6 g/cm^3 , lower than **SPd170** because of the higher fibre content (51% vs 44%). The porosities were lower

(5.8% vs 7.8%), which are consistent with the results obtained on the diameter scale up and this was attributed again to the longer holding time.

Fig. 5. Microstructure analysis of sample **SPd400** in different spots in the 400 mm large discs. For each spot, the fibre distribution, ceramic matrix and fibre/matrix interface were analysed and compared. Magnifications are the same in all frames.

The microstructure appeared mostly homogeneous, with a slight porosity gradient going from top, where few pores are visible and where the fibre/matrix interface is similar to that observed for **SPd170**. Very close to the bottom, densification appeared to be more intense, with lower residual porosity and some fibre over-reacted (see supplementary information, Fig. S2).

Finally, a camera picture of the **SPh160** and its microstructural features are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4d. The total weight of this piece was about 11 kilograms and despite the unfavourable diameter/height ratio, the densification cycle was very successful, as in the case of smaller scale samples. The final density was very similar to **SPd400** sample, 3.4 g/cm^3 . Microstructural features of this manufacture (Fig. 4d) compare very well with the features of the smaller samples. Details of the microstructure revealed a regular architecture,

thanks to the regularity of the fibre preforms. The fibre volumetric content was over 50 vol%, which explains the lower density. Other characteristics were similar to smaller samples, e.g. the matrix was nearly fully dense and the fibres well anchored to the matrix. No delamination between 0° and 90° layers was ever observed despite the thickness. Again, small portions of the manufacture were extracted from different positions, to check for homogeneity and an excellent reproducibility was found (see pictures in supplementary information, Fig. S3)

3.2 Densification and fibre/matrix interface.

All the sintering cycles were conducted at peak temperatures between 1800 °C and 1900 °C, with different heating and applied pressure rates, depending on the machine model and piece geometry. Despite the presence of carbon fibres, the densification of UHTCMCs proceeded successfully, similar to monolithic unreinforced ZrB₂-SiC systems fully sintered by hot pressing at 1900 °C [30]. SPS allowed densification at a lower temperature and was faster compared to hot pressing. Indeed, the time from the onset to complete shrinkage was as low as 27 to 42 min for the largest manufactures, despite the mass involved that went from few grams to kilograms. Interestingly, time needed for sintering a 400 mm large disc with a thickness of 5 mm, was longer than that for sintering of thicker samples with lower diameter, even with higher mass.

Production of 45 mm-thick samples allowed to study the densification behaviour through the analysis of the shrinkage. Typical shrinkage curves of hot pressed and SPSed samples with thickness of 45 mm are shown in Fig. 6a,b. For the hot pressing cycles, after the onset of densification at 1450 °C, two main slope changes in the shrinkage curve occurred. The corresponding shrinkage rate curve was deconvolved in two Pearson VII functions with peaks at 1750 °C and 1900 °C, Fig. 6a. Similarly, despite different conditions of temperature and applied pressure in SPS cycles, the displacement curve displayed a similar sigmoidal shape (Fig. 6b), with an onset temperature around 1390 °C and the corresponding shrinkage rate curve was decomposed into two pseudo-Voigt functions with main peaks at 1650 °C and 1770 °C; Fig. 6b.

The shrinkage curves just described can relate to chemical reactions occurring during densification, in turn deduced from microstructural observations. Since porosity was found in the matrix far from the fibres but never at the fibre-matrix interface, it was concluded that densification started preferentially at these sites. It is well known that C is an effective sintering additive for ZrB₂, therefore availability of C in the proximity

of the fibres helped to remove the oxide phases from ZrB₂ particle surface, e.g. B₂O₃ and ZrO₂, that usually hamper the densification [30]. Direct consequence of this finding was the formation of small ZrB₂ and ZrC particles that were frequently found around or embedded in the outer layers of the fibers (Fig. 6c). Newborn ZrB₂ particles were easily distinguishable from the starting powder grains for the tiny dimensions. The most probable reactions occurring during sintering involved C and oxide species present on the ZrB₂ and SiC particle surfaces e.g. ZrO₂, B₂O₃, SiO₂:

Diagram in Fig. 6d shows the variation of the free Gibbs energy as a function of temperature for each reaction. Apart from reaction 9, unfavourable in the whole temperature range of densification, the plot illustrates the sequence of reactions occurring at increasing temperature. Reactions 6 and reaction 7 were favourable starting from ~1500 °C and account for reaction occurring in the proximity of carbon fibres, with consequent formation of ZrB₂, as observed experimentally. Reaction 11, favourable for T > 1520 °C, is the carbo-thermal reduction of silica in the proximity of carbon fibers and was probably competing with reaction 7, in the consumption of silica. Reaction 10 accounts for formation of B₄C at T > 1570 °C, but since the latter was never observed, it was likely overwhelmed by other reactions. Reaction 8 followed at T > 1670 °C and accounts for formation of ZrC starting from ZrO₂ in the proximity of carbon fibres, in agreement with experimental observations. Finally, at T > 1750 °C, reaction 12, became favourable and accounted for the matrix densification, being the only one with no C among the reagents. This simplified analysis indicates that the dominant reactions during sintering were reactions 6,7 occurring at the matrix-fibre interface and reaction 12 occurring in the matrix far from the fibres, Fig. 6d.

Therefore, we can deduce that at around 1400-1450 °C, densification started with a solid-state rearrangement of the matrix grains and evaporation/condensation phenomena, then reactions 6 and reaction 7 started to occur resulting in a progressive increase of the shrinkage rate with a peak at 1750 °C or 1650 °C for hot pressing or SPS, respectively. Then, reaction 12 involving the matrix grains also comes into force, causing a marked acceleration of the shrinkage with a peak observed around 1900 °C for hot pressing (1770 °C for SPS). These stages are represented in curves deconvolved from the shrinkage rate one, see Fig. 6 a,b. Another interesting deduction is that since reactions 6,7 occur at temperature lower than reaction 8, a complete matrix densification is very likely accompanied by an overreacted fibre/matrix interface, as observed for samples like **SPd400**. As a matter of fact, the fibre/matrix interface was always very well bonded, with a resulting reduction of the fibre pullout.

Fig. 6. Shrinkage curves of 45 mm high samples during a) hot pressing cycles of **HPh45**, b) SPS cycles of **SPh45**. The deconvolution of the shrinkage rate curve was performed by using the Pearson VII and pseudo-Voigt function for the HPhed and SPSed samples, respectively, in order to obtain a fitting with a R^2 higher than 0.99. c) Matrix/fibre interface showing newborn ZrB_2 and ZrC particles anchored in the fibre and SiC particles embedded in the matrix. Inset: corresponding EDS spectra. d) temperature dependency of ΔG° for Eqs. 6-12 calculated with the HSC chemical package.

3.3 Thermo-Mechanical properties

The mechanical response of these composites is peculiar of a hybrid material comprising a very refractory and structural matrix, partially reacted fibres with unknown properties due to possible degradation during sintering and a well bonded fibre/matrix interface. Due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion between matrix ($7.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ [31]) and fibres ($-1.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ according to the supplier), residual stresses develop in the matrix that upon cooling down resulted in the formation of cracks [32,33]. Measured properties are summarized in Table 2. The number of tests performed was dependent on the final sample dimensions, therefore characterization was progressively more extended for larger samples. Overall, the properties were quite comparable between the different samples, see Table 2. Young's modulus and shear modulus values ranged from 125 to 150 GPa and from 20 to 35 GPa, respectively. These differences can be easily explained in terms of fibre volumetric content, which was higher for samples **SPd400** and **SPh160** compared to **SPd170**. As for the absolute Young's modulus values, the 0/90° sequence had about half the modulus compared to unidirectional 0/0° composites, 230–240 GPa [32]. Due to the higher stiffness of the constituent phases, ZrB_2 and carbon fibres, the composite moduli were generally much higher than those of C/SiC composites reported in literature [34].

In terms of room temperature bending strength there is a notable consistency of values (see Table 2) between a previously published sample [35], and samples **SPd170** and **SPh160**, all being around 230 MPa (load-displacement curves in Fig. 7a), despite the different thermal treatment, bar geometry, and testing methodology. For **SPd400**, the mean values were lower, a feature that was attributed to the previously mentioned defects in the carbon fibre cloths (Fig. 4), as well as the slightly overreacted fibres. Moreover, two

sets of bars extracted from different regions of this disc (**SPd400**) revealed a very limited scattering in the strength values, confirming the good homogeneity of the manufacture.

In previous works, the high temperature flexural strength of these composites was generally higher than room temperature values [12,15,36,37]. This trend was confirmed in this study, see the load-displacement curves in Fig. 7b, even for scaled up manufactures, with exception of sample **SPd170** where the high temperature value at 1800 °C was exactly coincident with the room temperature (Table 2). For samples **SPd400** and **SPh160** the flexural strength increased from about 180 MPa to 310 MPa and from 230 MPa to 360 MPa, at 1800 °C. The composite strength increase was attributed to the increase of strength of carbon fibres with temperature, [36] release of thermal residual stresses [32] and the refractoriness of the matrix. Such refractoriness was caused by carbo-thermal reduction of any residual oxide phase, as described in reactions 6-12, that strongly inhibited release of intergranular glassy films in the matrix [38,39].

As previously mentioned, measurement of the tensile strength was possible just for material **SPd400**. The room temperature tensile strength was lower than the bending strength, 120 MPa, in agreement with previous results [12,37] and increased to 200 MPa at 1600° – 1800°C (load-displacement in Fig. 7c).

Noteworthy, the load displacement curves of both bending and tensile strength (Fig. 7), showed the typical three-stage deformation trend at room temperature (Fig. 7 a,b, respectively). This 3-stage behaviour is common for ceramic composites with a brittle matrix, but in some cases (for **HPd50** and **SPd170**) we observed a stiffness recovery in the last stage up to almost the pristine value [13,37]. The second stage, characterized by a lower stiffness, is more evident in the case of bending curves of **HPd50** and **SPd170** samples and may be attributed to the matrix cracking and the consequent expansion of the inner freed fibres (IFF) [33]. This characteristic three-stage deformation trend is not present in case of tensile and bending tests at elevated temperature (Fig. 7 b,c, respectively) and bending test along the pile-up direction (Fig. 7d) owing to the release of the residual thermal stress and the lack of CTE mismatch, respectively [32].

Values of mechanical properties along the composite thickness (pile-up direction) are hardly found in the literature because composites are usually developed as flat plates with a limited thickness (<40 mm), which makes any meaningful mechanical characterization impossible along the thickness. The Young's modulus across the thickness was measured on samples **SPh160** and the resulting value, 25 GPa, was less than half of that of unidirectional 0/0° composites [33]. The strength measured along the pile-up direction,

ranged from 20 MPa (**SPh160**) to 30 MPa (**HPh45**). These values were about half the off-axis strength measured onto unidirectional 0/0° composites [33]. The lower value of 0/90° composites should be attributed to the strong anisotropy between the plies with 0° and 90° orientations that led to a residual stress concentration between the planes. Indeed, the fracture occurred mostly along the interfaces between 0 and 90° planes, which was the weakest zone (Fig. 8).

Table 2. Dimensions, densities, porosity and fibre volumetric amounts for the sintered pellets.

		HPd50	HPh45	SPd170	SPd400	SPh160	Averaged properties	C/SiC PIP LSI CVI properties range
		Ref.[35]	This work	This work	This work	This work	This work, Ref.[35]	Ref. [40] [41,42] [42]
Architecture		0/90°	0/90°	0/90°	0/90°	0/90°	0/90°	0/90° 2D 2D
Density	g·cm ⁻³	3.9 ± 0.1	4.0 ± 0.1	3.8 ± 0.1	3.5 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.1	3.7 ± 0.3	1.8 1.8–2.4 2.1–2.2
Porosity	%	8 ± 2	<2	8 ± 4	6 ± 3	9 ± 2	7 ± 4	10 <1–2 10–15
Fibre amount, V_f	%	40 ± 5	48 ± 2	44 ± 5	54 ± 4	50 ± 2	47 ± 7	46 - 42–47
Young's modulus, E	GPa	-	-	124 ± 2	137 ± 6	154 ± 16	138 ± 17	65 50–80 90–100
		-	-	-	-	25 ± 3 [±]	25 ± 3 [±]	- - -
Shear modulus, G	GPa	-	-	35±1	25±1	21 ± 1	27 ± 7	- - -
RT Flexural strength, σ_f	MPa	235±40	-	235±10	170±25-185±20	230 ± 40	220 ± 42	500 80–230 450–500
		-	30±4 [±]	-	-	16 ± 4 [±]	23 ± 9	- - -
σ_f at 1800 °C	MPa	-	-	240±4	320 ± 20	360 ± 60	307 ± 68	- - -
RT Tensile strength, σ_t	MPa	-	-	-	120 ± 7	-	120 ± 7	250 40–350 300–380
σ_t at 1600 °C	MPa	-	-	-	200 ± 24	-	200 ± 24	266 - -
σ_t at 1800 °C	MPa	-	-	-	200	-	200	- - -
Coefficient of thermal expansion, α	10 ⁻⁶ °C ⁻¹	-	-	3.3±0.1	-	5.1 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 0.1	1.2–2.7 3 3
		-	7.7±0.1 [±]	-	-	8.3 ± 0.1 [±]	8.0 ± 0.4 [±]	4.1–6.2 [±] - -
Thermal conductivity, k_{th}	W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹	-	140.0	-	-	-	140.0	11.3 13–40 5
		-	-	28.1 [±]	-	-	28.1 [±]	5.2 [±] - -

k_{th} at 1200°C–1500°C	$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$	-	108.3	-	-	-	108.3	12.2 20 5
		-	-	23.6 [±]	-	-	-	23.6 [±]

[±] Properties along the pile-up direction and measured on bars vertically machined.

Fig. 7. a) Stress-strain curves obtained through 4-point bending tests (HPh50) and 3-point bending test (SPd170, SPd400 and SPh160) at RT. b) Stress-strain curves obtained through 3-point bending test at 1800 °C; low pass FFT filter was applied to the SPd170 curves owing to the high noise recorded in the strain measurements. c) Stress-displacement curves obtained through tensile tests at RT, 1600 °C and 1800 °C. d) Stress-strain curves obtained through 4-point bending tests on bars machined along the manufacture thickness (pile-up direction).

As for the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) values measured on the 0/90° planes ranged from 3.3 to 5.1 $10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$. These values are consistent with the combination of the matrix CTE ($7.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ [31]) and the highly anisotropic CTE of carbon fibres, (spanning from near $0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ in the longitudinal section to $8\text{-}10 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ [43] in the transverse direction). The difference between SPd170 and SPh160 materials should be attributed to the misalignment error among the piled-up plies. In fact, it is reasonable that in case of SPh160 some plies with nominal 0° alignment were not well oriented leading to a higher CTE. Higher values of $7.7 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ and $8.3 \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$ were instead observed along the pile-up direction, as expected.

ZrB₂-enriched with carbon fibres were good thermal conductors, due to the high conductivity of the constituent phases. Monolithic ZrB₂ has a conductivity of 60 W/(m·K) [44] up to about 1500 °C. Carbon fibres have extremely high thermal conductivity along the longitudinal direction (320 W/(m·K), given from the supplier and much lower conductivities in the transverse direction (2-20 W/(m·K) [45,46]). Thermal conductivities (k_{th}) of these composites were of course highly anisotropic, being affected by the fibre disposal.

The good reproducibility of mechanical properties over a wide range of conditions and geometries is a key finding because it suggests that the properties are not too sensitive to process changes and this allows small samples to be characterized, saving time and cost. In view of that, representative values of the properties can be obtained by averaging the values obtained so far, see Table 2.

Fig. 8. a) Pictures of a vertically extracted slice from **SPh160** block and sketch of texture for the bending specimens. b) Fracture surface of a **SPh160** specimen bended with pile-up configuration, showing that fracture occurred at the interface.

3.4 Comparison with other UHTCMCs in the literature

Yet there are not so many reports on the mechanical properties of UHTCMCs and the results appear quite scattered due to the diversity of processing methods and raw materials adopted. Nevertheless, values obtained in this work are usually close to those obtained with the PIP technique as a consolidation method. H. Hu in [47] reported a flexural strength of 163 MPa for a C/SiC material enriched with about 25 vol% of ZrB₂, Q. Li [48] reported a bending stress of 248 MPa for a 3D-C/SiC enriched with 23 vol% of ZrB₂-ZrC

phases, L. Li [49] a value of 255 MPa for 2D-C/SiC enriched with a ZrB₂-TaC mixture. C_f/ZrC-SiC composites obtained with eight PIP cycles achieved a density of 4.19 g/cm³, and flexural strength of 286 ± 25 MPa [50]. Other reference values found in the literature are for HfB₂-based UHTCMCs obtained from 2.5D C_f needled preforms by the CVI technique achieving bending strength values in the range 96 – 166 MPa and tensile strength values of 70 – 88 MPa [20].

3.5 Fabrication of prototypes

This work has demonstrated that scale-up in diameter is feasible and does not substantially affect the material properties. The reason was the good sinterability of these composites which was not affected by an increase in dimensions. The vertical scale-up, as expected, was also viable, and the properties were highly anisotropic displaying very low modulus and strength and higher CTE along the thickness. Presence of defects related to the pile-up process were responsible for the low values of Young's modulus and strength and indicate that further process optimization is needed, especially for very thick manufactures. Despite the fact that the mass was increased by two orders of magnitude, the time required for the densification did not change. The change of sintering technique from hot pressing to spark plasma sintering allowed to sinter a much larger mass of material, but the sintering mechanisms were found to be the same.

From the manufactures presented in Fig. 3, prototypes for mechanical characterization (Fig. 9) and TPS (Fig. 9) and propulsion (Fig. 10) applications were successfully machined either with conventional machining tools or by electro-discharge machining. A TPS tile entirely made in sintered UHTCMC with dimensions 194 mm × 240 mm × 4 mm is shown equipped with UHTCMC standoffs assembled through UHTCMC screws and nuts, according to design presented in Fig. 1. The assembled model was tested in the hypersonic L3K plasma wind tunnel facility of DLR in Cologne [46].

Fig. 9. a) Dog bone bars for tensile strength tests; UHTCMC connectors: b) set of screws, c) Screw and nut d) Assembled UHTC TPS tile (194 mm × 240 mm × 4 mm) for hypersonic plasma wind tunnel tests, e) detail of the stand-off connection to the tile through screw and nut.

In parallel, nozzle prototypes were machined from thick manufactures, with an incremental approach, starting from small insert up to a nozzle as high as 120 mm, see Fig. 10. These models were assembled and tested in several types of rocket motors, as it will be illustrated in further publications.

Fig. 10. a) A set of nozzle demonstrators with various shapes and dimensions obtained from [HPh45](#), [SPh45](#) manufactures for testing in different rocket motors and b) the largest throat obtained for demonstration purposes from manufacture [SPh160](#). The inset in (b) is the top view of the nozzle demonstrator

3.6 Perspectives for the use of UHTCMCs vs C/SiC materials

UHTCMC materials of the present work have strength values still lower than C/SiC materials obtained by LSI, PIP, CVI (200-500 MPa, [51]), but as stated above, values increase notably at 1800 °C where C/SiC materials are out of their operational limit. Noteworthy, UHTCMCs have much higher densities, around 3.4 – 4 g/cm³, twice as high as C/SiC materials 1.8 – 2.2 g/cm³. The higher density and compactness is responsible for higher modulus (120 – 150 GPa vs 60 –100 GPa for C/SiC) but also higher thermal conductivity compared to C/SiC materials (10 – 40 W/(m·K) [40–42]) and CTE.

The key advantage of UHTCMCs comes from thermal stability at higher temperature than what conventional CMCs can offer, as well as from reusability potential. Arc-jet tests proved an exceptional stability at temperature up to 2200 °C [52].

Development of new technologies and materials require a final application in mind, especially for development passing TRL 3. Engineers must look at particular system applications and compare the effects of using different types of TPSs (thermal protection systems) on the same vehicle. In this respect, one possible application where UHTCMCs could offer a great advantage compared with SoA solutions is for the launcher upper stage. While there are reusable lower stages in use or in development, upper stage reusability

has been a greater challenge so far mainly due to much higher energy to be dissipated during re-entry. UHTCMCs could offer such potential of reusability still unachievable with other materials. SpaceX is currently working on Starship reusable orbital vehicle, which could essentially be considered a very large upper stage. Their commitment and investments to such technology may be seen as a support for the argument.

4. Conclusions

For the first time, sintered UHTCMCs based on $ZrB_2/SiC/C_f$ have moved out of the lab scale and into the industrial scale. This was necessary to produce near full-scale demonstrators for testing in relevant environments and to raise their technological readiness level.

Starting from cylindrical pellets of 50 mm, manufactures were scaled up in flat discs up to final dimensions of 400 mm diameter discs, thickness 5 mm. At the same time, scale-up in thickness was also attempted reaching a 160 mm height over a diameter of 170 mm. Despite an increase of mass of two orders of magnitude, the time required for the densifying the large samples was the same of small lab-scale samples. Properties and microstructures were compared from small and large discs, showing a good reproducibility, despite different processing and testing conditions. For the first time, tensile tests were carried out. The flexural and tensile strength tested in different geometries resulted in very similar stress-strain curves and reproducible values (about 240 MPa and 120 MPa for bending and tensile, respectively). The development of thick samples allowed the characterization of properties along the thickness, which showed that there is a strong anisotropy in properties related to the fibre architecture.

This paper shows that processing of the green manufactures resulting in homogenous distribution of fibre and matrix and sapient dosing of secondary phases led to highly sinterable composites that were indistinguishably consolidated either by hot pressing or by spark plasma sintering with adjustment of sintering parameters, up to the maximum size of available industrial furnaces. A piece of 11 kg was densified in about 30 minutes. To date, this was the largest piece of UHTCMC material ever produced so far. The manufactures were successfully machined to produce complex shapes and thick manufactures. A fully assembled TPS tile (194 mm × 240 mm × 4 mm), including UHTCMC screws, nuts and standoffs was designed and manufactured. A group of fifteen nozzles, from the smallest 20 mm high to the largest 160 mm high, was fabricated.

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6. Data availability statement

All data included in this study are available upon request by contact with the corresponding author.

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